

and

$$L_n = m_1 n_i \left(\frac{\partial^n J_1}{\partial X_1^n} \right)_0 + m_2 n_i \left(\frac{\partial^n J_2}{\partial X_2^n} \right)_0 + \dots + m_r n_i \left(\frac{\partial^n J_r}{\partial X_r^n} \right)_0 \dots (9)$$

respectively. Eqs. (8) and (9) suggest that such symmetries will depend on the constancy of n_i . The examples presented below will clarify the position further. Examples—

(a) When r is even ($r = 4$)

(Elements of rows 1 and 2, 3, and 4 being reciprocals)

$$L_{1112233344} = L_{1122233344} = L_{1222234444}$$

$$n_1 = 3, n_2 = 2 \quad n_1 = 2, n_2 = 3 \quad n_1 = 1, n_2 = 4$$

$$n_3 = 3, n_4 = 2 \quad n_3 = 2, n_4 = 3 \quad n_3 = 1, n_4 = 4$$

(b) When r is odd ($r = 5$) and elements of lone (5th) row are unity (Elements of rows 1 and 2, 3 and 4 being reciprocals)

$$L_{11122334455} = L_{1233445555} = L_{1111222234}$$

$$n_1 = 2, n_2 = 2 \quad n_1 = 1, n_2 = 1 \quad n_1 = 4, n_2 = 4$$

$$n_3 = 2, n_4 = 2 \quad n_3 = 2, n_4 = 2 \quad n_3 = 1, n_4 = 1$$

$$n_5 = 2. \quad n_5 = 4. \quad n_5 = 0.$$

(c) When r is odd and the elements of the lone (5th) row are a constant or different (Elements of rows 1, and 2, 3 and 4 being reciprocals)

$$L_{11122234455} = L_{1233344455} = L_{1111222255}$$

$$n_1 = 3, n_2 = 3 \quad n_1 = 1, n_2 = 1 \quad n_1 = 4, n_2 = 4$$

$$n_3 = 1, n_4 = 1 \quad n_3 = 3, n_4 = 3 \quad n_3 = 0, n_4 = 0$$

$$n_5 = 2. \quad n_5 = 2. \quad n_5 = 2.$$

The success and failure to observe the special symmetries to hold in some earlier communication³ thus gets explained on the basis of this generalised discussion.

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Microdetermination of 3-methyl-3-(3',5'-dibromo-2', 4'-dihydroxyphenyl) tetrachlorophthalide using ceric sulphate as oxidising agent

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THE dye (I) has been reported in literature by Singh and Gupta¹, and has been shown to be useful as an adsorption indicator² by the same authors.

In the present communication the authors have described quantitative determination of (I) in micro amounts using Ceric sulphate as an oxidising agent in presence of a large excess of acid. Since acetic acid is one of the main oxidation products requiring 50 equivalence, probably the following reaction takes place

In the reaction of the dye (I) acetic acid was isolated and identified as mentioned in the discussion.

Experimental

Reagents used : Dye (I) prepared from *o*-acetyl-tetrachlorobenzoic acid³ by the method¹; ferrous ammonium sulphate, sodium carbonate, sodium bicarbonate, sulphuric acid, and sodium hydroxide (AnalaR, B.D.H. grade); *N*-phenyl-anthranilic acid (B.D.H. grade); ether solvent (Alembic); and Ceric sulphate (Technical B.D.H. grade).

Apparatus used : Micropipettes and microburettes used had least count = 0.01 ml; hot plate with a regulator for heat control.

Standard solution of the dye was prepared by dissolving an exactly weighed sample in 1% NaOH solution.

Standard ferrous ammonium sulphate solution was prepared by dissolving an exactly weighed amount in 0.01N H₂SO₄ solution.

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NOTES

TABLES

Microdetermination of 3-methyl-3-(3',5'-dibromo-2',4'-dihydroxyphenyl)tetrachlorophthalide using ferrous ammonium sulphate 0.005N

Dye (I) 0.000472M	H ₂ SO ₄ 16N	Ce(SO ₄) ₂ 0.002N	Ferrous ammonium sulphate 0.005N	Ferrous ammonium sulphate (employed) 0.005N	Amount of dye (I)		Error %
					Taken × 10 ⁻²	Found × 10 ⁻²	
ml	ml	ml	ml	ml	mg	mg	
—	7.5	10	14.74	—	—	—	—
0.3	7.5	10	13.32	1.42	8.10	8.10	0.0
0.6	7.5	10	11.86	2.88	16.20	16.47	1.6
0.9	7.5	10	10.44	4.30	24.30	24.60	1.2
1.2	7.5	10	9.00	5.74	32.40	32.80	1.2
1.5	7.5	10	7.58	7.16	40.50	40.84	0.8

Microdetermination of the above dye (I) using ferrous ammonium sulphate 0.004N and dye 0.2 to 1.2 ml.

Dye (I) 0.000472M	H ₂ SO ₄ 16N	Ce(SO ₄) ₂ 0.002N	Ferrous ammonium sulphate 0.004N	Ferrous ammonium sulphate (employed) 0.004N	Amount of dye (I)		Error %
					Taken × 10 ⁻²	Found × 10 ⁻²	
ml	ml	ml	ml	ml	mg	mg	
—	7.5	10	15.02	—	—	—	—
0.2	7.5	10	13.85	1.17	5.40	5.35	0.9
0.4	7.5	10	12.67	2.35	10.80	10.75	0.5
0.6	7.5	10	11.46	3.56	16.20	16.26	0.4
0.8	7.5	10	10.24	4.78	21.60	21.69	0.4
1.2	7.5	10	8.98	6.04	27.00	27.45	1.6

Note: The use of 7.5 ml 16N H₂SO₄ for the oxidation of 0.2 to 1.5 ml of the dye shows maximum error 1.6% only, but by decreasing the hydrogen ion concentration the percentage error is raised.

0.002N Ceric sulphate (in 16N H₂SO₄) solution was prepared and standardised by titrating against standard ferrous ammonium sulphate solution using N-phenyl-anthranilic acid as an indicator.

0.1 g N-phenyl-anthranilic acid and 0.2 g Na₂CO₃ were mixed together and dissolved in about 20 ml of distilled water shaking vigorously. After dissolving it was transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask and the volume was raised to the mark by adding more distilled water.

Procedure

Known volumes of dye (I) solution were taken in different conical flasks fitted with air condensers, and known excess of standard of Ceric sulphate, and sulphuric acid solutions were added along with 5 ml distilled water. The flasks containing the reaction mixtures were placed on a hot plate at full heat till the boiling started, then heating was continued at lower temperature for 120 min. After cooling to room temperature the remaining Ceric sulphate was titrated against ferrous ammonium sulphate using N-phenyl-anthranilic acid as an indicator. At the end point the reddish-brown colour disappears sharply.

Results and Discussion

The results are given in the above Tables. The ranges in which dye (I) has been estimated by

oxidising with Ceric sulphate vary from 8.10×10^{-2} mg to 40.84×10^{-2} mg and from 5.35×10^{-2} mg to 27.45×10^{-2} mg.

The reaction between dye (I) and Ceric sulphate in presence of large excess of sulphuric acid required 25 oxygen atoms for complete oxidation resulting in the rupture of the molecule to Cl₂, Br₂, CO₂, and CH₃COOH.

The reaction mixture was acidified with solvent ether. The ethereal extract was washed and thoroughly shaken with a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate. The sodium bicarbonate extract was acidified and extracted with ether. The organic layer was washed and then concentrated at low temperature. Only one compound (acetic acid) was identified from the concentrate by paper chromatography and further confirmed by co-chromatography with authentic sample.

Since the reaction between dye(I) and Ceric sulphate in presence of H₂SO₄ is completed at 50 equivalence, hence, the observed experimental values have been divided by its equivalence while making calculations.

References

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